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A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF AGRICULTURE GROWTH IN INDIA AND CHINA

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INTRODUCTION

The economies of the world's poorest countries are overwhelmingly agrarian; those of rich countries are dominated by manufacturing and services. Perhaps because of agriculture's initial pre-eminence, a classic literature has argued that agricultural development is either a prerequisite to industrial development, or that it carries important 'forward linkages' to other sectors of the economy (Rosenstein-Rodan, 1943; Schultz, 1953; Lewis, 1954; Rostow, 1960). This view has been influential with policymakers: the World Bank (2007, p. 7) states that "success stories of agriculture as the basis for growth at the beginning of the development process abound" citing England, Japan, India, Vietnam and China as prominent examples of agriculture led growth.

In China, higher agricultural surpluses led to higher savings, capital accumulation and, ultimately, non-agricultural output. In another parallel to China, many of these Asian countries also undertook successful agricultural reforms around time they began to industrialise. Post-war land reforms in Japan, South Korea and Taiwan redistributed land to peasants and are thought to have increased agricultural output (Dore, 1959; Thorbecke, 1979; Jeon and Kim, 2000). More recently, the decommunalisation of agriculture in Vietnam in the mid 1980s dramatically increased agricultural output (Pingali and Xuan, 1992) and raised the curtain for a sustained period of rapid growth that continues to this day. In each of these cases, increases in agricultural output due to the reforms could have increased the supply of capital to the non-agricultural sector—just as it did in China.

China's success in manufacturing holds several lessons for India but China's performance in agriculture is no less remarkable. Over the past few decades, rapid agricultural growth has allowed the Chinese growth engine to pick up pace without stoking inflation.

Unlike the advanced economies of Western Europe and North America, farm growth in China has been driven by small landowners rather than by industrial farming. As per National Sample Survey Organization data, the average size of operational holdings in India fell to 1.2 hectares in 2010-11 from 2.3 hectares in 1970-71. China's average holdings are even smaller. According to the 2000 World Census of Agriculture, the average size of Chinese holdings was 0.6 hectares. Thus, farming in both countries is dominated by small farmers.

Despite the similarities, Chinese agriculture has fared better than Indian agriculture on most counts over the past few decades. Both India and China are among the world's top three producers of important crops such as rice, wheat, cotton and maize, but China produces much more from each hectare of land than India does.

In the early 1960s, farm sector indicators of India and China looked similar, but since then China has left India behind. According to Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) data, the ratio of value of agricultural production (in constant 2004-06 international dollars) in China and India was 0.99 in 1960. By 1990, this ratio became 1.66 and 2.23 in 2010.

China's overall economic success cannot be understood without a careful reading of its agricultural sector. The manner in which China put in place incentives for small farmers and supported them through sizeable public investments in agriculture and rural electrification holds important lessons for India. At the same time India, must guard against policies responsible for large-scale rural discontent, which can have drastic consequences in a democratic set-up.

PRODUCTIVITY COMPARISONS OF INDIA AND CHINA

An India Vs China comparison – both are large countries with similar sized populations and same common food consumption habits – is interesting. For starters, China has less area under cultivation, consumes less fertiliser and yet produces more. Total food grain production of China touched 571 million tonne in 2012 as compared to India's 250 million tonne in 2011-12.

Agricultural productivity, to be fair, also depends on a variety of factors like soil quality, availability of water, use of fertilizers and use of high yielding variety of seeds. But productivity also becomes important in India because roughly 50% of the population still derives their livelihood from agriculture. India's irrigation coverage was a poor 48.3% of total cultivated area as late as 2008-09. Which means a bad monsoon can cause havoc.

Let's now look at the top five producing countries for two crops – paddy (rice) and wheat.

T-1 Crop Productivity in Top Five Countries

Crop & Country	Area under cultivation (Million Hectare)	Total Production (Million Tonne)	Productivity (Tonne/Hectare)	% Share in world production
PADDY				
World	158.30	685.24	4.2	100
CHINA	29.88	196.68	6.5	28.7
INDIA	41.85	133.70	3.1	19.5
Indonesia	12.88	64.40	4.9	9.4
Bangladesh	11.35	47.72	4.2	6.9
Vietnam	7.44	38.90	5.2	5.6
WHEAT				
World	225.62	685.61	3.0	100
China	24.29	155.11	4.7	16.7
India	27.75	80.68	2.9	11.7
Russia	26.63	61.74	2.3	9.0
USA	20.18	60.31	2.9	8.8
France	5.14	38.33	7.4	5.5

The first thing to note from the above **Table** is that India was the second largest producer of both paddy (rice) and wheat behind China. However, India lagged in productivity levels.

India had the worst productivity of 3.1 tonne/hectare in paddy against a world average of 4.2 tonne/hectare. In wheat production, India stood fourth among the top five countries with a productivity of 2.9 tonne/hectare. The only country behind India was Russia.

USE OF FERTILIZERS IN INDIA AND CHINA

Now, let's look at some countries and see how much fertiliser they used per hectare in 2008 (This is not an argument for use of fertiliser). We will look at a few Asian countries, especially the ones that had higher productivity than India in rice production.

T-2 Use of Fertilizers in selected Asian Countries

Sr. No.	Country	N+P2O Kg./Hectare
1	CHINA	83.7 Kg./Hectare
2	INDIA	120.2 Kg./Hectare
3	Indonesia	67.6 Kg./Hectare
4	Bangladesh	134.8 Kg./Hectare
5	Vietnam	157.8 Kg./Hectare

Incidentally, fertiliser use has steadily gone up in India since 1950-51 when only 0.6 million tonne (Nitrogen, Phosphorous and Potassium variety) was used. In 2010-11, the fertiliser use stood at 2.8 million tonne.

As **Table 2** shows, the relation between fertiliser use and productivity is not very obvious. China, the most productive country in wheat and rice, used much less fertiliser than India, which was the second largest producer in both crop categories.

Vietnam, which was ranked 2nd in paddy productivity, used the maximum fertiliser among the top 5 countries. Indonesia, which was 3rd in terms of productivity, used the least amount of fertiliser. India used a lot of fertiliser: 138.6 kg/hectare but failed to increase productivity to the levels of China or Vietnam. So what could be the reasons for India lagging China in agricultural productivity?

Here are some general pointers gleaned from reports in public domain. China has many pro-farmer policies. Priorities are given to high-yield bulk crops (grain, cotton, oil and sugar) and grants are provided for grassland ecological conservation. Some other programmes adopted by China for agricultural development include:

Vegetable Basket Programme: Started in 1989, the **VBP** project aims to increase production and utilise natural resources reasonably. In the first five years, 14.05 billion Yuan in investment (roughly Rs 12,290 crore) was used for scientific and technical development.

By 1997, output of almost all products had increased by 10%. Incidentally, this programme concentrates more on non-food grain products. In India, the reliance is more on basic food grains like rice and wheat.

Returning Grazing lands to Grasslands: This was an important programme for China's development. It was started with an accumulated investment worth 9.319 billion Yuan (Rs 8,152 crore) and more than 30 million hectare grazing lands has been turned to grasslands.

China has also started **collective water management**. Under this programme, villages hire a manager who operates directly under local government directive. Water managers collect water-use fees from farmers.

This may or may not be an accurate comparison as the figures may not match but India's agriculture budget (2012-13) is Rs 27,931 crore. In contrast, China spent, [as per media reports](#), \$164 billion on agricultural products, around Rs 913,398 Crore. In general, increasing agricultural productivity in India would depend on better irrigation coverage, more effective use of fertilisers, farmer education and soil management.

But steps like the Accelerated Irrigation Benefit Program (AIBP) to several fast-track irrigation initiatives have not yielded results. These are of course general pointers and not an agriculturist's prescription. The data however is something to ponder over.

CONCLUSION

As of now both are fast developing economies in the world and also most populous countries and having population reached at 1.4 billion and 1.2 billion. Despite the similarities, Chinese agriculture has fared better than Indian agriculture on most counts over the past few decades. Both India and China are among the world's top three producers of important crops such as rice, wheat, cotton and maize, but China produces much more from each hectare of land than India does. The manner in which China put in place incentives for small farmers and supported them through sizeable public investments in agriculture and rural electrification holds important lessons for India. At the same time India, must guard against policies responsible for large-scale rural discontent, which can have drastic consequences in a democratic set-up.

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